

Extractive Spectrophotometric Determination of Selenium with Potassium Propyl Xanthate

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Several methods have been reported for the determination of microgram amounts of selenium with various reagents¹. In the present investigation a simple, sensitive spectrophotometric method has been reported for the determination of selenium using potassium propyl xanthate (KPX) as a reagent. The advantages of the present method are that the extraction occurs in wider range of pH and concentration and the stability is comparable to the earlier methods. The method has been successfully applied for the determination of microamounts of selenium in real samples.

Results and Discussion

The absorption spectrum of Se-KPX complex in CCl₄ (most suitable solvent) showed an intense peak at 320 nm. The extraction was found to be quantitative in the pH range 4.0–8.0. Further studies were carried out at pH 6.0 using 0.2 M sodium acetate-acetic acid buffer. The extraction was found to be quantitative for equilibration time >1 min. The complex was found to be stable for 10 h.

The experiments carried out varying the concentration of the reagent showed that 2 ml of 0.66% solution of the reagent was sufficient for quantitative complexation. Beer's law was obeyed over a concentration range of 0.625–14 µg ml⁻¹ of Se. On constructing Ringbom plot the exact concentration range 1.25–10.00 µg ml⁻¹ of Se could be determined accurately. The molar absorptivity was found to be 6.5 × 10³ dm³ mol⁻¹ cm⁻¹ at 320 nm and Sandell's sensitivity 0.012 µg cm⁻². Standard deviation, coefficient of variation, confidence limit and standard error for 10 determinations of 100 µg/8 ml of Se were found to be 0.0518, 0.0518%, ± 0.0370 and 0.0172 respectively. The composition of the selenium(IV) complex was found by mole-ratio method and Job's method of continuous variation. Equimolar solutions (8.86 × 10⁻⁴ M) of selenium and reagent were used for these studies. The ratio of metal-to-reagent was found to be 1 : 4.

Interference due to a number of ions in the determination of 12.50 µg ml⁻¹ of Se was studied. U^{VI} and Hg^{II} formed complexes with the KPX but they were not extracted in CCl₄. Among the cations, Mg^{II} and Ba^{II} upto 3750 µg, Sr^{II}, Zn^{II} and Ce^{III} upto 5000 µg did not interfere. Among the anions, phthalate, bicarbonate, thiocyanate and bromide upto 5000 µg, acetate upto 4000 µg, tartrate upto 3800 µg, phosphate upto 3500 µg and chloride upto 1250 µg did not interfere. Interferences due to Pb^{II} (500 µg), Co^{II} (250 µg), Sn^{II} (150 µg), Cr^{VI} (150 µg), Cd^{II} (500 µg) and

Mo^{VI} (150 µg) were avoided using 2 ml of 4% EDTA as a masking agent. The interference of Fe^{III} (150 µg) was masked using 1 ml of 1% hydroxylamine hydrochloride. Among the anions tested citrate was found to interfere in the determination of selenium.

The developed method was applied for the analysis of water samples and cabbage leaves spiked with 2 to 12.50 µg ml⁻¹ of Se. The results show that the method is applicable for the determination of selenium with the percentage recovery of 98.4%. The method was also applied for the analysis of selenium in cadmium selenide thin film and synthetic mixtures corresponding to the alloys of Se-Fe (42.6–51.8% Fe), Se-Hg (72% Hg) and Se-Pb (72.41% Pb). The results presented in Tables 1 and 2 respectively.

TABLE 1—DETERMINATION OF SELENIUM IN CADMIUM SELENIDE THIN FILM
pH ~6.0, KPX = 2 ml of 0.66%

Certified composition*	Amount of Se taken µg	Amount of Se found µg	Average µg	Recovery %
Se-48.80	40.00	39.06		
Si-10.28		39.12	39.20	98.0
S-1.83		39.33	(0.3326)	
Cd-38.73 ^a		39.29		
Zn-0.36		59.21		
	60.00	59.02	59.12	98.5
		59.24	(0.2601)	
		59.01		

*Certified by IIT, New Delhi. ^aCadmium was masked using 2 ml of 4% EDTA. Coefficient of variation (%) is given in the parenthesis.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF SELENIUM IN SYNTHETIC MIXTURES

Alloy	Se(µg ml ⁻¹)		Standard deviation
	Taken	Found*	
Hg-Se	0.75	0.73	0.1743
	1.25	1.26	0.1433
	2.15	2.12	0.1153
Pb-Se	1.00	0.98	0.1562
	1.42	1.41	0.1311
	2.30	2.27	0.1058
Fe-Se	0.80	0.77	0.1664
	1.20	1.18	0.1442
	1.75	1.78	0.1248

*Average value of three determinations.

Experimental

A Shimadzu PR-1, UV-240 spectrophotometer with 1 cm quartz cells and an Elico LI-120 pH meter with glass electrodes were used.

The chemicals used were of A.R. grade Standard selenium(IV) solution (1 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving selenium dioxide in concentrated HCl (1 ml) and in deionised double-distilled water and standardised². Potassium propyl xanthate (KPX) was prepared³ and purified⁴. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from their corresponding salts. Buffers of different pH values were prepared by mixing 0.2 M solutions of sodium acetate-hydrochloric acid (pH 1-3), sodium acetate-acetic acid (pH 4-6) and ammonium hydroxide-ammonium chloride (>pH 7).

Procedure : To an aliquot of selenium solution (5-120 µg), acetate buffer (2 ml) and 0.66% KPX (2 ml) were added and the aqueous phase was maintained to 8 ml with deionised double-distilled water. The solution was allowed to stand for 40 min for the completion of the reaction. The Se-KPX complex was shaken for 2 min with CCl₄ (8 ml), the organic layer separated and the absorbance measured at

320 nm against the reagent blank. The reagent had negligible absorbance at this wavelength.

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References

- 1 Q DUAN, D XIE and D WANG, *Huanjing Huaxue*, 1985, 4, 70 (*Chem Abstr*, 103, 81010), T A KUL'BEDA, E S BESKOVA and A I GAMOLINA, *Tr Khim Khim Tekhnol*, 1975, 1, 24 (*Chem Abstr*, 87, 161083), T A KUL'BEDA, E S BESKOVA and G I ZHURAVLEV, *Khim Promst Ser Reakt*, 1979, 5, 22 (*Chem Abstr*, 93, 87879), N SINGH and A K GARG, *Analyst*, 1986, 111, 247, X LI and Y LIU, *Fenxi Huaxue*, 1988, 16, 25 (*Chem Abstr*, 110, 224567), A DAS and J DAS, *J Indian Chem Soc*, 1983, 60, 67, R S BROWN, *Anal Chim Acta*, 1975, 74, 441, B KASTERKA, *Chem Anal*, 1992, 37, 361, K N RAMACHANDRAN, R KAVEESHWAR and V K GUPTA, *Talanta*, 1993, 40, 781, H LI and X ZHANG, *Yejin Fenxi*, 1992, 12, 18 (*Chem Abstr*, 118, 204296)
- 2 R N SAREN and S P PANDEY, *J Inst Chem*, 1983, 55, 205
- 3 A I VOGEL, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 3rd ed., Orient Longmans, London, 1969
- 4 S R RAO, "Xanthates and related Compounds", Marcel Dekker, New York, 1971